

**CITATION ANALYSIS OF PH.D. THESES ON ECONOMICS
SUBMITTED TO DR. BABASAHEB AMBEDKAR
MARATHWADA UNIVERSITY**

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Abstract

A citation analysis of Ph.D. theses submitted to Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Library was performed as a way of determining the use of information sources made by the scholars of the university. for the present study 34Ph.D.theses of Economics were chosen as a sample from the year 2000-2010,there are in all 2876 citations appended in 34 theses. The data was collected from the bibliographical entries listed at the end of the theses, which was used by the researchers for completing the theses. The citations were photocopied and the data was collected. Citation analysis have been carried out to find the types of cited document, the chronological distribution of cited documents, to find out the authorship pattern of cited document. The rank list of cited journals books, to find out the language. Wise distribution, geographical distribution of cited documents, the rank list of cited web – sources and the cited authors.

Keywords:

Citation analysis, Bibliometrics, Ph.D. Theses, Economics, Web-Citations, P-Citations Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University.

INTRODUCTION:

Citation analysis is a major area of bibliometrics research, which use various methods to establish relationship between authors and their work (Ane's Encyclopedic Dictionary of Library and Information Science, 2006).

Citation analysis is a technique of bibliometrics. It is an important research tool understanding the subject, which we analyze the structure and direction of the subject. It measures the utility of documents and relationship between their author and their documents.

Citation analysis is an important tool used by the librarian, teachers and Information scientist to represent the relationship which exists between the cited and citing document, the technique of citation analysis involve the process of collection, counting and analysis given in various types of literature. This is the direct method to analyze the library record to determine the actual sue of the documents. These types of information can provided useful idea for acquisition of important material selection of document etc. this can helps libraries, it also helps the information system designers, to plan their products and services.

THE MAIN OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY ARE:

- Chronological distribution of cited documents.
- Authorship pattern of cited document.
- Geographical distribution of cited document.
- Raking of journals.
- Ranking of books.

- Language – wise distribution of cited documents.
- Ranking of cited web-resource.
- Difference between Web- citation and P-citation.
- Raking of prolific authors.

SCOPE AND LIMITATION:

The present study is based on 2876 citations appended at the end of 34 Ph.D. theses on economics, submitted to Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad. The span of 10 years was taken into consideration that is from 2000-2010.

METHODOLOGY:

For the present study 34 Ph.D. theses of Economics were chosen as a sample from the year 2000-2010, there are in all 2876 citations appended in 34 theses. The data was collected from the bibliographical entries listed at the end of the theses, which was used by the researchers for completing the theses. The citations were photocopied and the data was collected. The analysis was done by using various parameters.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The study of citation analysis Based on references has appeared in the 34 Ph.D. theses of economics submitted to Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Aurangabad. The studies like (Kannappanava , 1991; Berhanuddin, 1992; Sangam, 1986; Thoidingjam, 1997; Mistra, 1997; Chikate, 2008) found useful for the study.

Bibliometrics is the most active field of library and information science. Citation analysis study is the major portion of it. Bibliometrics is a sub field in the information science – Bibliometrics is the study of documents and their bibliographic reference and citation structure. Bibliometrics methods have been successfully applied to examine the intellectual structure of several disciplines (Schneider, 2004).

Bibliometrics involves the quantitative analysis of the literature of a subject domain, as represented by bibliographic entries such as key words, classification codes, authors and citations, purpose of the bibliometrics study is to find out the growth and characteristics of digital literature. The major objectives of the bibliometrics study are to find out authorship pattern, author productivity, prolific authors, core journals in subject area, indexing terms frequency, Bradford distribution of articles, year – wise distribution of articles, language –wise distribution of articles and country – wise distribution of journals (Singh, 2007). “Bibliometrics”, Informetrics”, “Scientometrics” and “Technometrics” are unfortunately not very clear and there is choice in the terminology (Wormell 1998).

Citation represent the pool of archival knowledge from which authors retrieve established ideas and, in turn generate new research ideas. This knowledge may be disseminated; within an area and across disciplinary boundaries (Sharif, 2004). Citation count and Impact factors can be easily manipulate (Gorman, 2005). Citation impact can be used as a measure of the impact an article has within its particular field. An article being widely read and cited is an indication that it has had influence with other researchers within the field (Turk, 2008).

Citation analysis focuses on the investigation of the relationship between the citing and cited documents or the link expressed in the references (Tang, 2008, Sharif, 2004). Citation analysis is an important tool used to trace scholarly, measure impact, and justify tenure and funding decisions. It allows a research to follow the development and impact of an article through time by looking backward at the references the author cites, and forward to those author who then cite the article (Bauer and Bakkalasi, 2005). The review of literature shows the use –fullness of citation analysis study to the librarians and researchers in the various disciplines.

DEFINITIONAL ANALYSIS:

To gain clarity and consistency the following terms are used with the meanings given below for the purpose of the study.

CITATION ANALYSIS:

Paul and Roy (1983) defined citation analysis as, "Citation analysis is one branch of bibliometrics where the unit of analysis is a document, that is a document, that is being cited as a bibliographic reference of as a foot note in citing document". (P. 226)

PH.D. THESIS:

Sengupta (1991) defined thesis as "A thesis is a statement of investigation of research presenting the authors findings and any conclusions reached, submitted by the author in support of his candidate for a Ph.D. degree in Science".

ECONOMICS:

Economics is a social science that studies how society chooses to allocate its scarce resources, which have alternative uses, to provide goods and services for present and future consumption.

Political Economy or Economics is a study of mankind in the ordinary business of life. It examines that part of individual & social action which is most closely connected with the attainment & with the use of material requisites of well-being. Thus, it is on one side the study of wealth and on the other important side it is the study of man."

DR. BABASAHEB AMBEDKAR MARATHWADA UNIVERSITY:

The state legislature passed the Marathwada University Act, 1958 to establish and incorporate a teaching and affiliating university at Aurangabad. The act received assent of the governor on may 5 and the university was inaugurated on August 23, 1958. From May 21, 1974 the university is governed by Act. No. XXV of 1974 passed by the Marathwada legislature and assented to by president of India. The University was renamed as Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University in January 1994. At present the university has 33 departments. Economics is one of the oldest department.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1. FROM WISE DISTRIBUTION OF CITED LITERATURE:

The table No. 1 depicted that out of 2876 citations 1664 (57.86%) citations were from books, so it can be said that the most of the authors or researchers depends up on the books literature for their study, were as reports 552 (19.19%), Journals 394 (13.70%), Government Publication 117 (4.07%) and remaining citations were collected from Thesis, News Papers, web sites, and gazetteers.

Table No. 1

Form Wise Distribution of Cited Literature

Sr. No	Types of Document	Citation	Percentage
1	Books	1664	57.86
2	Reports	552	19.19
3	Journals	394	13.70
5	Gov.Pub	117	4.07
6	Thesis	77	2.68
7	News Papers	43	1.50
8	Web Site	26	0.90
10	Gazetteers	3	0.10
	Total	2876	100.00

Fig.No 1: Form Wise Distribution Cited Documents

2. CHRONOLOGICAL DISTRIBUTION OF CITED DOCUMENTS:

From the table No.2 and Figure No. 2 it was seen that the duration of the whole period is divided in various groups from 1908 to 2010. It was observed that, the highest numbers of citations were in 1999-2008 that is 977 (33.97%) and lowest numbers of citations were in 1908-1918 that is 7 (0.24%).

Table No. 2

Chronological Distribution of Cited Documents

Sr. No	Year	Citation	Percentage
1	1908-1918	7	0.24
2	1919-1928	15	0.52
3	1929-1938	17	0.59
4	1939-1948	30	1.04

5	1949-1958	64	2.23
6	1959-1968	171	5.95
7	1969-1978	248	8.62
8	1979-1988	369	12.83
9	1989-1998	531	18.46
10	1999-2008	977	33.97
11	2009-2010	2	0.07
12	Year not mentioned	445	15.47
	Total	2876	100.00

Fig No 2: Chronological Distribution of Cited Documents

3. Authorship Pattern of Documents:

The table No. 3 and Figure No. 3 indicates that out of total number of 2876 citations 2094 (72.81%) are by single author, followed by 394 (12.13%) have two authors, the least

Citations are by five authors, i.e. 1 (0.03%).

Table No.3
Authorship Pattern of Documents

Sr. No	Authors	Frequency	Percentage
1	Single Author	2094	72.81
2	Two Author	349	12.13
3	Three Author	44	1.53
4	Four Author	8	0.28
5	Five Author	1	0.03
6	Not available	380	13.21
	Total	2876	100

Fig No 3: Authorship Pattern of Documents

4. Ranking of Journals:

The journals which are highly cited in document, that journal is most important to keep in the library, for that purpose journal ranking is essential for the librarian as well as researchers.

The rank lists of cited journals are taken from 2876 citations from various forms of cited documents. The journals were grouped into different ranks, according to their frequency occurrence in the total number of citation only first 7 ranked journals have been given in table No. 4.

Table No. 4

Ranking of Journals

Sr. No	Title of Journal	Frequency	Rank	Percentage
1	Maharashtra sinchan vikas	40	1	10.15
2	Arthabodh	25	2	6.35

3	Shetkari	12	3	3.05
4	Yojna	7	4	1.78
5	The Maharashtra cooperative quartly	5	5	1.27
6	Arthasanwad	3	6	0.76
7	Baliraja	3	6	0.76
8	Economic and political weekly	3	6	0.76
9	Rashtrachi shrimanti aani garibi Navbharat	2	7	0.51
10	Reserve bank of india bulletin	2	7	0.51
11	Chitralkha	2	7	0.51
12	Co-operative perspective	2	7	0.51

5. Ranking of Books:

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Books are the most reliable medium for communication and spread of knowledge. From the table No. 5 it was observed that out of 2876 citation, 1664 citations were book citations. Only 10 ranked books have been given in table No, 5 which were most preferred by the researchers of economics.

Table No. 5

Ranking of Books

Sr.No	Name of Book	Citations	Rank	Percentage
1	Zillah Osmanabad	15	1	0.90
2	Samajik Sanshodhan padhati	13	2	0.78
3	Marathwada	12	3	0.72
4	Indian economy	11	4	0.66
5	Co-operative movement in india.	9	5	0.54
6	Sthanik Swarajya Sanstha	8	6	0.48
7	The mega state maharashtra.	7	7	0.42
8	Panchayati rajya.	7	7	0.42
9	Co-operation in india.	7	7	0.42
10	Bharatiya arthawayastha	7	7	0.42
11	Basic development statistics of marathwada region.	6	8	0.36
12	Irrigation and economic development	6	8	0.36
13	Maharashtra 2004	6	8	0.36
14	Theory,History and practice of cooperation	5	9	0.30

15	Samajshariya Sanshodhan tatwa aani padhati.	5	9	0.30
16	Oudyogik samajsashtra	5	9	0.30
17	Maharashtratil jillhe	5	9	0.30
18	Bharat me sthanik sasan ka itihās.	5	9	0.30
19	Bharat me loktantrik vikendrikaran our nav panchayati raj	5	9	0.30
20	Rural development	4	10	0.24

6. Language Wise Distribution of Cited Documents:

The total numbers of 2876 citations were distributed among 3 different languages as shown in Table No. 6 and Figure No. 4 the 1505 (52.33%) citations were in English language, and 1316 (45.76%) citations were in Marathi language and remaining 55(1.91%) citations were in Hindi language.

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Table No.6

Language Wise Distribution of Cited Documents

Sr. No	Language	Citation	Percentage
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1	English	1505	52.33
2	Marathi	1316	45.76
3	Hindi	55	1.91
	Total	2876	100.00

Fig No 4: Language Wise Distribution of cited Documents

7. Geographical Distribution of Cited Documents:

Geographical analysis of citations provides information of the range of countries active in the field and their relative contribution.

It was found in the present study some of the citation have not given the country of publications. It was observed that 1972 (68.75%) citations were from India and 58 (2.02%) citations were from England and 48 (1.67%) citations were in U.S.A. and remaining citations were in Nepal, Australia, Bangladesh, Netherland, Scotland and Switzerland.

8. Ranking of Web Citations:

The ranking of web- citations. Help the scientist to select the web-site of maximum utility in relation to their coverage of new and important literature in particular subject area. The Table No. 7 shows that, total number of 2876 citations out of that only 26 (0.90%) citations were web-citations and 2850 (99.10%) were P-citations out of that 26 web-citation 'http://district.mah.nic.in, http://rural.nic.in and etc. scored the top with 2 (7.69%) citations,

followed by all citations goes to second rank respectively.

Table No.7 Ranking of Web Citations

Sr. no	URL Web-sites	Citation	Rank	Percentage
1	http://district.mah.nic.in.	2	1	7.69
2	http://rural.nic.in	2	1	7.69
3	http:www.The hindu.com	2	1	7.69
4	http://www.census india.net/	2	1	7.69
5	http://www.helsinki.fi/iehe2006	1	2	3.85
6	http://www.mapsofindia.com	1	2	3.85
7	http://www.nird.org.	1	2	3.85
8	http://www.puradue.co-operatives.org/ content/global/file/historal.pdf	1	2	3.85
9	http://www.Sheti.com	1	2	3.85
10	http://www.ssi.nic.in/schpmry.html	1	2	3.85
11	http://www.ukrweekly.com/archive/2004 /0300416.html	1	2	3.85
12	mced_agd@sancharnet.in	1	2	3.85
13	www.divisionalofficer.gov.in. Amravati	1	2	3.85
14	www.google.co.in	1	2	3.85
15	www.indiabudget.nic.in	1	2	3.85

16	www.laghu.udyog.com	1	2	3.85
17	www.marathwada.gov.in industry	1	2	3.85
18	www.smallindustry.india	1	2	3.85
19	http/www.midcindia.org. udyojak@vsnl.com	1	2	3.85
20	http://agricoop.nic.in	1	2	3.85
21	http://mahaeges.nic.in	1	2	3.85
22	http://planning commission. nic.in	1	2	3.85
	Total	26		100.00

9. Difference between P-Citations and Web-Citations:

From the table No. 8 and Figure No. 5; it was observed that there were total 2876 number of citation out of them 2850 (99.10%) citation were P-citation (Printed- citations) and only 26 (0.90%) citation were web-citation or E-citations.

Table No.8: Difference between P-Citations and Web-Citations

Sr. No.	Types of Citations	Frequency	Percentage
1	P-Citations	2850	99.90%
2	Web-Citations	26	0.90%

Fig No 5. Difference between P-Citation and Web Citation

10. Ranking of Authors:

The author ranking is essential for to find out the predominant author in the particular subject area, it is useful for researchers, librarians and students.

The rank list of cited authors are taken from 2876 citations from authors were grouped into different ranks, according to their frequency occurrence in the total citation. Only first 10 ranked authors have been given the table No. 9.

Table No. 9 Ranking of Authors

Sr.No	Authors Name	Citation	Rank	Percentage
1	Maharashtra Sasan	104	1	3.17
2	Government of India.	64	2	1.95
3	Jillha samajik va aarthik samalochan	22	3	0.67
4	Artha wa sankheki Sanchalnalaya	19	4	0.58
5	Dastane,Santosh.	18	5	0.55

6	Kurulkar,R.P.	16	6	0.49
7	Gare,Govind	14	7	0.43
8	Jillha parishad aurangabad	13	8	0.40
9	Garge,S.M.	11	9	0.34
10	Bhandarkar,P.L.	11	9	0.34
11	Reserve bank of India.	10	10	0.30

CONCLUSIONS:

The study of citation analysis of 34 Ph.D. theses on Economics shows that most cited documents in physics literature are from Books (57.86%) and remaining (42.14%) citations were from reports, journals, Government Publication, theses and others. So it was concluded that, researchers depend more on books literature for their investigations. The chronological distribution of citations shows that maximum number of citations are covered during the period of 1999-2008 i.e. 977 (33.97%). The authorship pattern of citations shows that the single authored citations are more in number that others that is 2094 (72.81%). Ranking of journals shows that the journal of 'http://district.mah.nic.in, http://rural.nic.in and etc.' ranked first which was highly cited journal by authors. The books are the most reliable medium for communication and spread knowledge, the title of book 'Zillah Osmanabad' is the first rank book with. 15 (0.90%) citations. The language wise distribution of citations shows that 1505 (52.33%) documents were cited in English Language hence we conclude that English is predominant language regarding books and journals in the economics. The geographical distributions shows that the Indian literature is mostly used for the research by the researchers that is 1972 (68.57%). The ranking of web citation shows that only 26 (0.90%) citations are web citation and remaining 2850 (99.10%) citations are P-citations. It was also observed that difference between P-Citation

and web-citation shows that the printed resources were mostly referred by the researchers. The ranking of authors depicted that 'Maharashtra Sasan' is the first ranked author with 104 (3.17%) citations.

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